

SCAFFOLDING. NURTURING LEARNERS' PROFICIENCY IN CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

In the field of education, scaffolding refers to the instructional technique that provides temporary support to learners as they acquire new knowledge, skills, or competencies. Originally developed by psychologist Lev Vygotsky, scaffolding has proven to be a powerful approach in language teaching, enabling educators to guide students through challenging tasks and gradually withdraw support as learners gain independence. This paper explores the concept of scaffolding in teaching English as L2, its benefits and practical strategies to implement it effectively in a content and language integrated learning (CLIL) classroom. Descriptive method of data collection, exactly questionnaires, were used in this particular research. The study implies various Scaffolding techniques as Modeling, Bridging, Contextualizing, Schema Building and Metacognition for teaching English language with integration to Media for students of Uzbekistan Journalism and Mass Communication University.

Keywords: *Scaffolding, Content and Language integrated Classroom, Autonomous learning, Student-centered classroom, Modeling, Bridging, Contextualizing, Schema Building, Metacognition, Media English*

Being psychological, but board concept, Scaffolding was successfully integrated to education by Burner in 1970s. According to Burner, Scaffolding is an interactional instructional approach to teaching, while teacher enables learner to overcome a problem independently. (Wood, Burner and Ross, 1976: 90). Generally, Scaffolding is a method of teaching, that empowers students' autonomy and minimized teacher' interference (van de Pol, Volman and Beishuizen, 2010). This method includes several techniques like:

- Modeling refers to the instructional strategy where a teacher or more knowledgeable peer demonstrates a specific skill, task, or thought process to a learner. The purpose of modeling is to provide a clear example that helps the learner understand how to approach and perform the desired activity.

- Contextualizing in scaffolding refers to the process of adapting or adjusting the scaffolding system to suit the specific requirements and conditions of a particular work environment or project. It involves considering various factors such as the

curriculum layout, classroom features and unique challenges to ensure that the scaffolding is appropriately designed and implemented.

- Schema building in scaffolding refers to the process of constructing a well-organized and efficient scaffolding system by systematically planning and arranging the various teaching components and structures involved. It begins by assessing the project requirements, including the scope of work, timelines, and specific needs.

- Metacognition in scaffolding refers to the process of promoting and supporting learners' awareness and control of their own thinking and learning strategies within a scaffolding framework. It involves helping learners to develop a reflective and strategic approach to their learning by consciously monitoring, evaluating, and adjusting their thinking processes and learning strategies.

The classroom, where additional language is incorporated into content or non-language classes is defined as Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) classroom. (Coyle, Hood and Marsh, 2010) CLIL students are supposed to face various challenges because of shortcomings in comprehension of teacher's instructions. (Cummins and Early, 2015) Thus, utilization of Scaffolding techniques to gain language support and interpret meaning beyond their current proficiency level is successful way to overcome these challenges. (Gibbons, 2015) Moreover, Scaffolding in CLIL can become a bridge over gap between what learners can do independently and what they can achieve with assistance, ultimately fostering their linguistic development. (Raymond, 2000)

Despite the promotions of benefits of Scaffolding in language teaching by several researchers, there are some challenges and limitations associated with implementing scaffolding in CLIL. As Mahan, Brevik and Ødegaard note, investigations in this specific are limited and require further studies. (2018) It is important to be aware of these challenges and address them effectively. Some of the challenges include:

- Time Constraints: Scaffolding requires careful planning and implementation, which can be time-consuming for teachers. Creating scaffolded activities, providing individualized support, and giving timely feedback all require additional time and resources. Teachers must strike a balance between scaffolding and covering the necessary curriculum.

- Varying Student Needs: Each student has unique learning needs, and it can be challenging to provide personalized scaffolding for a diverse group of learners. Teachers must assess students' language proficiency levels, identify their specific areas of weakness, and adapt scaffolding techniques accordingly. This requires a deep understanding of individual learners and the ability to differentiate instruction effectively.

- **Overreliance on Scaffolds:** If scaffolds are not gradually removed or faded, learners may become overly dependent on them. Over time, this can hinder their ability to work independently and apply language skills without external support. Teachers must carefully monitor and adjust the level of scaffolding to ensure that learners are gradually developing autonomy.

- **Language Complexity:** Scaffolding complex language skills, such as advanced grammar structures or nuanced vocabulary, can be challenging. It may require teachers to break down the language into smaller, more manageable parts and provide appropriate support at each stage. Balancing the level of challenge and support is crucial to ensure that learners are appropriately scaffolded without being overwhelmed.

- **Assessment and Evaluation:** Assessing learners' language proficiency and progress while considering the scaffolding provided can be complex. Traditional assessments may not accurately reflect students' true abilities if they have heavily relied on scaffolds during the learning process. Teachers need to employ a variety of assessment methods that capture both supported and independent language use to gain a comprehensive understanding of learner progress.

- **Limited Resources:** Scaffolding often involves the use of additional resources such as visual aids, technology tools, or supplementary materials. However, not all educational settings may have access to these resources. Teachers need to be creative and resourceful to provide effective scaffolding within the constraints of their available resources.

The scaffolding metaphor is an advantageous concept that enables instructors to shift away from the direct instruction of a traditional classroom and search for a richer and more sophisticated educational tool. In addition, it is important to note, that during the lessons the students do not produce any tangible goods (texts, posters, or presentations). Owing to the term's metaphorical connotations, scaffolding may be understood as any form of assistance in general or even as a variant on direct instruction. When scaffolding is interpreted as a form of direct instruction, it might impede students' growth into engaged, independent learners. Besides, teachers will be more able to employ the scaffolding metaphor creatively and rationally if they have a greater understanding of the theoretical foundations of the metaphor.

Scaffolding is a powerful instructional approach in language teaching that supports learners' progress and proficiency. By providing targeted support, individualized instruction, and opportunities for independent practice, teachers can foster linguistic development and empower students to become more proficient language users. Incorporating effective scaffolding strategies in language teaching helps create a supportive learning environment where students can confidently

navigate the complexities of language acquisition and achieve their language learning goals.

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